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MUTUAL IMPACT OF INDUSTRY AND THE ENVIRONMENT

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***Annotation.** The mutual impact of and the environment acts as a component of the ecological system "man - nature". The most pressing environmental issues at present are the following: global pollution of the natural environment; environmental education of people; disposal of industrial and human waste; ensuring normal life and health of people, etc. Analysis of the results of the conducted research by scientists showed the possibility of using flotation waste. In the compositions of ceramic masses, depending on the properties of the clay component, they can act as leaning additives improving drying and shrinkage properties; mineralizers intensifying sintering processes; as a component that helps increase the strength and heat resistance of the material; posing additives to reduce the bulk density of products.*

***Key words.** Industry, ecological system, waste, flotation waste, ceramic masses.*

The main direction of environmental protection today is the maximum possible maintenance of ecological balance and ensuring natural ecosystem interrelations. The mutual impact of industry and the environment acts as a component of the ecological system "man - nature". The most pressing environmental issues at present are the following: global pollution of the natural environment; environmental education of people; disposal of industrial and human waste; ensuring normal life and health of people, etc.

The increase in mineral extraction, the development of metallurgical production and thermal power engineering have led to a significant accumulation of various types of waste, which are generated both in the process of extraction and enrichment of minerals, and at various stages of their processing [1]. The soil is polluted by solid waste from the metallurgical industry. It accumulates on land areas of hundreds of hectares. The largest amount of solid waste is formed during the production of cast iron. There are 400 kg of slag per ton of metal.

Heavy metals tend to accumulate in soil, water, plants, food, the human body, etc. Metallurgical plants and complexes occupy areas of more than a thousand hectares, the majority of which are occupied by dumps, sludge ponds and other waste.

They penetrate the soil under the influence of precipitation, and this area becomes unsuitable for agriculture. The environmental problem causes millions of losses to the economy, and also affects the human body, leading to pulmonary, oncological, vegetative-vascular lesions, disorders of the musculoskeletal system, diseases of the skeletal system, dermatitis, etc.

Research by many scientists on the use of various technogenic wastes has established the possibility of their use in the ceramic industry. Unlike many other manufacturing industries, the ceramic industry is able to reuse within its production the main part of its own wastes, which are formed at a certain stage (often as purifiers) of production [2]. The development of production technology actually allows the use of a large part of production waste, reusing it in the ceramic production cycle instead of other raw materials. In this way, it is possible to avoid the extraction, transportation and use of thousands of tons of natural materials such as sand, feldspars, aluminum oxide, zirconium oxide, mullite, clays. The use of effective substitutes for feldspar materials in ceramic masses, in colored coatings and ways of improving the physical, technical and technological properties of ceramics have led to the use of “tailings” of ore enrichment, previously not used in the domestic ceramic industry for these purposes, as a complex substitute for feldspar, pegmatite and Fe_2O_3 for the production of ceramic products [3].

Metals that enter the environment are divided into three hazard classes, the moderately hazardous class includes the following: nickel, cobalt, copper, chromium, molybdenum, etc. The Kaitash tungsten-molybdenum plant produces molybdenum and a large amount of solid waste is formed during the flotation process. According to the obtained DTA data of the initial flotation waste (Kaitash tungsten-molybdenum production), the endothermic effect at 173°C on the thermal curves characterizes the removal of hygroscopic water. The exothermic effect at 430°C corresponds to the combustion of organic impurities. The endothermic effect at 580°C is caused by the removal of crystallization water and partial destruction of the kaolinite crystal lattice, and the endothermic effect at 846°C is caused by polymorphic transformations of quartz.

The endothermic effect with a maximum at 980°C is accompanied by the appearance of new phases - mullite, anorthite. The diffraction pattern of the flotation waste reveals the following phases: quartz $d/n = 0.421; 0.3350, 180 \text{ nm};$ kaolinite $0.511; 0.197 \text{ nm};$ wollastonite $d/n = 0.317; 0.287; 0.197; 0.148 \text{ nm},$ hydromica $d/n = 0.511; 0.335;$ hematite $d/n = 0.269; 0.251; 0.227; 0.186 \text{ nm}.$ The infrared absorption spectra of the Kaitash flotation waste of tungsten-molybdenum ores are characterized by the presence of absorption bands at wave numbers of 1050, 940, 910, 680, 650 cm^{-1} , which belong to the quartz-like framework $[\text{Si}(\text{Al})\text{O}_4]$.

Symmetrical stretching vibrations of Si-O-Si are observed at 810 cm^{-1} , which indicates the existence of ring anions $[\text{Si}_3\text{O}_9]^{6-}$. The bands at 1050 and 450 cm^{-1} characterize the frequencies of Al-O-Al absorption bands in the region of wave numbers 540 and 450 cm^{-1} are related to stretching vibrations of Fe-O-Fe. The indicated absorption bands are also observed in the infrared spectrum of natural hematite at 810 cm^{-1} , they are related to the deformation vibration of the Fe-O bond. Thus, the characteristics of the Kaitash flotation waste from the enrichment of tungsten-molybdenum ores show that, based on the Al_2O_3 content, it can be assigned to various classes of refractory with some approximation, based on the CaO content, one can judge the temperature of deformation of products, based on the Fe_2O_3 content, the color of fired products, based on the SiO_2 and alkalis Na_2O and K_2O content, the fusibility of raw materials and the strength of finished products [4].

Therefore, in order to develop a method for recycling flotation waste and the possibility of obtaining facing tiles based on Angren kaolin clays, flotation waste and glyage, it was planned to develop a ceramic base with improved physical and mechanical properties. The use of waste from the ceramic industry, in particular, the Kaitash tungsten-molybdenum production, makes it possible to reduce the consumption of scarce raw materials, as well as reduce the harmful effects of man-made waste on the environment, and improve the economic performance of production.

Analysis of the results of the conducted research by scientists showed the possibility of using flotation waste. In the compositions of ceramic masses, depending on the properties of the clay component, they can act as leaning additives improving drying and shrinkage properties; mineralizers intensifying sintering processes; as a component that helps increase the strength and heat resistance of the material; posing additives to reduce the bulk density of products [5]. In this way, two problems are solved simultaneously: the identification of new raw materials and the solution to the problem of environmental pollution. Heavy metals are so toxic that they can affect the soil within a radius of 200 km from waste dumps, and within a radius of 100 km, all vegetation is completely destroyed. Production waste pollutes the soil in areas adjacent to enterprises, and there is contamination of drinking water sources, an increase in diseases and an increase in mortality.

Literature

1. U. B. Aleksandrovich et al., Ecology and production of building materials. System technologies, journal- 2015 - №1/22 pp.84-88.
2. Secondary raw materials in the production of building materials. Reference manual. Ed. A. V. Dolgorev. - M.: Stroyizdat, 1990. 496 p.
3. Mukhamedzhanova M. T. Flotation waste of a lead-zinc factory in tile compositions // Glass and ceramics. 1996. - № 10. - pp.21-23.
4. Makarov N. A., Sverdlikov V. L. Composite material of the corundum - zirconium dioxide - sintering additive system. // Glass and ceramics. 2005. - № 11. - pp.8-10.
5. Artikov A., Mukhamedzhanova M.T. Industrial waste for the production of ceramic tiles // Construction materials. 2003. – No. 2. – P. 52-53.